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Original Research Article

Aug. 25, 2021

My Lord, my wife Hyeonhi did not sleep well because she has continued to make Ailyne sleep during the night! (Tcheonzamun 401st-416th)

Dr. Anis Ahmad

Associate Editor

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A Study on Korean Language Education Evaluation System in China-with Special Focus on the Training of Korean Interpreters and Translators

 Lim Hyungjae, Flourish Kamei

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